

Is the U.S. stock market a bubble after the 2020 stock market crash?

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Abstract

After the stock market crash in 2020, the US stock market seems unstoppable, with the S&P 500 index soaring 173.5% in less than five years. Based on the log-periodic power law singularity (LPPLS) method, we systematically investigate the bubble status of sectors with different total market capitalization levels of U.S. stocks through four major U.S. stock market indexes, including the Wilshire 5000 Total Market index, the S&P 500 index, the S&P MidCap 400 index, and the Russell 2000 index, which represent the overall stock market, large-cap stocks, mid-cap stocks and small-cap stocks, respectively. We find that the peak confidence indicator of these four indexes all exceeds 19% after November 2024, which indicates that the price trajectories of these four stock market indexes have clearly featured the obvious LPPLS bubble pattern of the faster-than-exponential growth corrected by the accelerating logarithm-periodic oscillations and are indeed in a positive bubble regime. The accelerating growth trends of these four indexes are likely unsustainable, and the positive bubble regime may change in the form of a sharp crash or volatile sideways plateaus.

Key Words: Stock market bubble, Log-periodic power law singularity (LPPLS), LPPLS confidence indicator, Financial bubble.

1. Introduction

The US stock market seems unstoppable after the stock market crash in 2020, with the S&P 500 index soaring 173.5% in less than five years. However, the U.S. Treasury yield curve has been inverted for more than two years, from July 6, 2022, to August 26, 2024. The negative spread between 10-year Treasury bonds and 2-year Treasury bonds widened to 108 basis points on July 3, 2023. This is an extremely rare situation, as the last time the negative spread exceeded 100 basis points was in 1981, more than 40 years ago. The abnormal inversion of the U.S. Treasury yield curve indicates that bond buyers and sellers expect the U.S. economy to slow down in the near future and have lost confidence in the stability of the economy in the coming years. Since the yield curve inversion has occurred before every U.S. recession since 1955, this could be a very bad economic signal.

This study employs the log-periodic power law singularity (LPPLS) model to systematically investigate the bubble status of sectors with different total market capitalization levels of U.S. stocks. Four major U.S. stock market indexes are used in this study, including the Wilshire 5000 Total Market (W5000) index, the S&P 500 (SP500) index, the S&P MidCap 400 (SP400) index, and the Russell 2000 (R2000) index, representing the benchmarks for the market value of all stocks actively traded in the United States, the 500 large capitalization stocks, the middle capitalization stocks, and the small capitalization stocks listed on the U.S. stock exchanges, respectively.

In the LPPLS model syndicates the mathematical and statistical physics of bifurcations and phase transitions, the economic theory of rational expectations, and behavioral finance of herding of

traders and defines a positive (or negative) financial bubbles as a process of unsustainably faster-than-exponential growth (or drop) to reach an infinite return in finite time, resulting in a short-term correction shaped by the symmetry of discrete scale invariance (Sornette, 1998). The LPPLS model captures two distinct characteristics of price trajectories in bubble regimes to detect financial bubble, i.e., the faster-than-exponential growth due to positive feedback by imitation and herding behavior of noise traders, and the accelerating log-periodic volatility fluctuations of the price growth due to expectations of higher returns and an upcoming crash. In recent years, the LPPLS model has been widely used to diagnose bubbles and crashes in various financial markets, including the stock markets (Demirer et al., 2019; Shu, 2019; Shu & Song, 2024a, 2024b; Shu & Zhu, 2020a, 2022; Song et al., 2022; Sornette et al., 2015) and the cryptocurrency market (Shu & Zhu, 2020b; Wheatley et al., 2019).

2. Log-Periodic Power Law Singularity Model

The LPPLS model is based on the idea of a risk neutral rational agent with rational expectations, ignoring the arbitrage, dividends, the interest rate, risk aversion, information asymmetry and the market clearing condition. The simple mathematical formula of the LPPLS can be described as (Filimonov & Sornette, 2013):

$$\text{LPPLS}(t) \equiv E[\ln p(t)] = A + B(t_c - t)^m + C_1(t_c - t)^m \cos[\omega \ln(t_c - t)] + C_2(t_c - t)^m \sin[\omega \ln(t_c - t)] \quad (1)$$

In Equation (1), $p(t)$ represents the observed asset price, A is the expected value of the log-price at the critical time t_c , which is the most probable time for a regime change in a form of a major crash or a great change of growth rate. In a bubble regime, the power parameter m ranges between 0 and 1, ensuring that the price remains finite at t_c , while the expected logarithmic price diverges at t_c . In the LPPLS model, there are three nonlinear parameters (t_c, m, ω) and the four linear parameters (A, B, C_1, C_2). Using the L^2 norm, the sum of squares of residuals of the LPPLS formula can be expressed as:

$$F(t_c, m, \omega, A, B, C_1, C_2) = \sum_{i=1}^N [\ln p(\tau_i) - A - B(t_c - \tau_i)^m - C_1(t_c - \tau_i)^m \cos(\omega \ln(t_c - \tau_i)) - C_2(t_c - \tau_i)^m \sin(\omega \ln(t_c - \tau_i))]^2 \quad (2)$$

where $\tau_1 = t_1$ and $\tau_N = t_2$. The 4 linear parameters (A, B, C_1, C_2) can be analytically solved using the following matrix equations

$$\begin{pmatrix} N & \sum f_i & \sum g_i & \sum h_i \\ \sum f_i & \sum f_i^2 & \sum f_i g_i & \sum f_i h_i \\ \sum g_i & \sum f_i g_i & \sum g_i^2 & \sum g_i h_i \\ \sum h_i & \sum f_i h_i & \sum g_i h_i & \sum h_i^2 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \hat{A} \\ \hat{B} \\ \hat{C}_1 \\ \hat{C}_2 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \sum \ln p_i \\ \sum f_i \ln p_i \\ \sum g_i \ln p_i \\ \sum h_i \ln p_i \end{pmatrix} \quad (3)$$

The three nonlinear parameters (t_c, m, ω) can be estimated by solving the resulting nonlinear optimization problem:

$$\{\hat{t}_c, \hat{m}, \hat{\omega}\} = \arg \min_{\{t_c, m, \omega\}} F_1(t_c, m, \omega) \quad (4)$$

To solve this optimization problem, this study employs the covariance matrix adaptation evolution strategy. Sornette et al.(2015) defined the LPPLS confidence indicator as the fraction of fitting windows in which the LPPLS calibrations satisfy the specified filter conditions to measure sensitivity of observed bubble pattern to the time interval between the end time and the start time in the fitting windows. A larger LPPLS confidence indicator, a more reliable LPPLS pattern. A small value of the LPPLS confidence indicator indicates a possible fragility because the few fitting

windows exhibits LPPLS pattern. We shrink the fitting window length from 650 trading days to 30 trading days in steps of 5 trading days for a given fictitious “present” data point t_2 to create a series of fitting time windows. To ensure model rigorousness, the search space is set to (Shu & Zhu, 2020b):

$$m \in [0,1], \omega \in [1, 50], t_c \in \left[t_2, t_2 + \frac{t_2 - t_1}{3} \right], \frac{m|B|}{\omega \sqrt{c_1^2 + c_2^2}} \geq 1 \quad (5)$$

The calibrated LPPLS model is filtered under the following constrains to determine the valid LPPLS fits:

$$m \in [0.01, 0.99], \omega \in [2, 25], t_c \in \left[t_2, t_2 + \frac{t_2 - t_1}{5} \right], \frac{\omega}{2} \ln \left(\frac{t_c - t_1}{t_c - t_2} \right) \geq 2.5, \\ \max \left(\frac{|\hat{p}_t - p_t|}{p_t} \right) \leq 0.20, p_{lomb} \leq \alpha_{sign}, \ln(\hat{p}_t) - \ln(p_t) \sim \text{AR}(1) \quad (6)$$

3. Empirical analysis

We detect both positive and negative bubbles in the U.S. stock markets based on the LPPLS confidence indicator by using the daily data of the W5000, SP500, SP400, and R2000 indexes from January 2, 2020, to January 31, 2025 (<https://finance.yahoo.com/>). We calculate the LPPLS confidence indicator by shrinking the length of time windows $t_2 - t_1$ from 650 trading days to 30 trading days in steps of 5 trading days, resulting in 125 fitting windows for each t_2 . The endpoint t_2 is moved from January 2, 2020, to January 31, 2025. A positive bubble is when an asset's price is accelerating upward at an unsustainable rate. This makes it vulnerable to sudden changes, which can be either a rapid crash or a period of unstable, sideways price movement. In contrast, a negative bubble is when an asset's price is accelerating downward too quickly. This kind of trend is likely to end with either a significant rally (a sharp upward correction) or, similar to a positive bubble, a volatile period of sideways price action.

Figure 1 shows the results of the LPPLS confidence indicator for these four US stock market indexes, in which the positive bubbles is shown in red and negative bubbles in green (right scale) along with the index price in blue (left scale). We can intuitively sense the confidence level of the LPPLS bubble pattern detected in the price trajectories, as the confidence indicator measures the sensitivity of the fitting results to the choice of starting time.

Figure 1 (a) shows the detected bubble status of W5000 index, including two obvious clusters of positive bubbles after 2020 stock market crash, that is, between November 30, 2020 and December 17, 2021, with the peak value of 0.112, and between March 21, 2024, and January 31, 2025, with the peak value of 0.264, and one subtle cluster of negative bubble between June 13 and November 9, 2022. The positive LPPLS confidence indicator peaked at 0.264 on November 25, 2024, indicating the 33 out of 125 fitting windows meet the filter conditions, confirming that the price trajectory of W5000 index is in a positive bubble regime. The accelerated growth trend of the W5000 index is extremely unsustainable, and the positive bubble regime of the W5000 index tends to change in the forms of a fluctuating sideways platform or a sharp crash.

The similar detected positive bubble patterns shown in Figure 1 (a) for the W5000 index can also be found in the remaining subfigures in Figure 1, including: (b) SP500, (c) SP400, and (d) R2000. Since 2024, the positive LPPLS confidence indicator peaked at 0.224 on July 29, 2024, and December 26, 2024, for the SP500 index, peaked at 0.192 on November 8, 2024, for the SP400 index, and peaked at 0.256 on December 2, 2024, for the R2000 index. It indicates that the US stock market enter positive bubble regime since late 2024.

Furthermore, the US stock market experienced a negative bubble regime in second half of 2022, with all four indexes showing negative bubble clusters as shown in Figure 1.

(a)

(b)

Figure 1: LPPLS confidence indicator for positive bubbles is shown in red and negative bubbles in green (right scale) along with the index price in blue (left scale) for the four U.S. stock market indexes based on daily data from January 2020 to January 2025.

4. Conclusions

This study uses the LPPLS methodology to systematically analyze the bubble status of U.S. equities sectors with different levels of total market capitalizations through four major U.S. stock market indexes W5000, SP500, SP400 and R2000. The results show that the peak confidence indicators of all four indices have exceeded 19% since November 2024, indicating that the price trajectories of these four stock market indices have clearly exhibited the characteristics of an LPPLS bubble. The accelerated growth trend of these four indices is likely unsustainable, and the positive bubble regime may shift to a sharp crash or volatile sideways movement.

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